

Studies in Formation and Properties of Carbon-Sulphur Surface Complexes: Part IV. Oxidation of Combined Sulphur by Different Oxidising Solutions

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Charcoals associated with sulphur as a result of interaction with different reagents were treated with various oxidising solutions and the amount of sulphur recovered as sulphuric acid was estimated in each case. The results indicate that a part of the sulphur is fixed as the reactive sulphide, hydrosulphide and sulphone groups and is released as sulphuric acid. A considerable amount of sulphur is retained by charcoal even on prolonged treatment with excess of hot concentrated nitric acid. This is supposed to be fixed at unsaturated sites or in replacement of combined hydrogen and to be present in the nuclei of the multiple closed chain structures constituting the layer-planes of the crystallites. The nature of the sulphur groups formed as well as the nature of the sites involved depend upon the sulphurising reagent employed for the fixation of sulphur.

It has been shown in previous publications from this and other laboratories that treatment of charcoal or carbon black with sulphur^{1,2}, hydrogen sulphide^{2,3}, carbon disulphide^{3,4} or sulphur dioxide^{1,5} results in the fixation of an appreciable amount of sulphur giving rise to stable carbon-sulphur surface complexes of indefinite composition and unknown structure. The amount of sulphur fixed has been shown to vary not only with the nature of the sulphurising agent employed but also with surface area² and hydrogen content^{1,3} of the carbons. The combined sulphur can be recovered as hydrogen sulphide and carbon disulphide on high-temperature evacuation or only as hydrogen sulphide on treatment with hydrogen at 1000°. There are indications that sulphur is fixed partly at the 'unsaturated sites'^{1,2} and partly by interaction with oxygen or oxy-hydrogen groups present on carbon surface^{1,3}. However, the nature of the functional and other groups which result from the fixation of sulphur has not been elucidated. The infra-red spectroscopy cannot be of much help in view of opaque nature of the materials concerned. The present paper describes an attempt made to find out the nature of the sulphur groups formed on treatment of charcoals of varying oxygen contents with different sulphurising agents, by reacting the products with various oxidising solutions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sugar and coconut charcoals prepared in the manner described before⁷ were outgassed at 400° and 1000°⁷ and then treated with hydrogen sulphide³, carbon disulphide³, sulphur¹ or sulphur dioxide¹ at the optimum temperature of 600°. The products were extracted

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with carbon disulphide in a soxhlet for 7 days. The amount of combined sulphur was determined by treating 0.5 g. of the products, in each case, in a current of hydrogen at 1000° and estimating the amount of hydrogen sulphide evolved.

Several one gram portions of each product were treated with aqueous bromine in KBr, aqueous chlorine, potassium chlorate solutions in hydrochloric acid and concentrated nitric acid. The suspensions in the first three cases were shaken mechanically for 72 hr. which was found to be sufficient for the end point while those with concentrated nitric acid were heated at 110° in an oil bath for about half-an-hour. The amount of sulphur oxidised as sulphuric acid was estimated gravimetrically. The values in a few cases were checked by estimating the amount of sulphur retained by the residual charcoal on treatment with hydrogen at 1000° as before. The agreement was within one per cent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The amounts of sulphur oxidised on reacting H_2S -treated or sulphur-treated 400° -outgassed sugar charcoal with different oxidising solutions are shown graphically in Figures 1, a, b, c and d. It is seen, in the first instance, that the amount of sulphur released as sulphuric acid on treatment with aqueous bromine (fig. a) or chlorine (fig. b) increases with increase in the concentration of the solutions employed and that the amount released with aqueous chlorine is much more than that with aqueous bromine of the same concentration. The values obtained with potassium chlorate (fig. c) are seen to rise with increase in the concentration of hydrochloric acid in the solution and those with hot concentrated nitric acid (fig. d) with increase in the amount of the acid used. However, ultimately a maximum amount of sulphur was released which, except in the case of chlorine water where it was not possible to raise the concentration beyond 0.2 N, did not increase further on raising the concentration of the oxidising solution employed. It is significant to note

Fig. 1. Amount of sulphur recovered as sulphuric acid on interacting charcoal containing sulphur with (a) aqueous bromine, (b) aqueous chlorine, (c) acidified potassium chlorate, and (d) concentrated nitric acid.

that as much as 50% of the total combined sulphur is retained even when such a drastic treatment as that with excess of hot concentrated nitric acid or that with highly acidified potassium chlorate is given. The fact that only a part of the combined sulphur can be recovered, the amount varying with the nature and concentration of the oxidising solution employed, and the fact that an appreciable amount of the combined sulphur remains intact under all conditions indicate that sulphur is fixed at more than one site and that it gives rise to more than one kind of sulphur group.

The maximum amounts of sulphur recovered as sulphuric acid on treating the various products with different oxidising solutions at optimum concentrations are given in table 1. The amount of sulphur originally fixed is also given in a separate column. It is seen that the amount of sulphur recovered by using a particular oxidising solution depends upon the nature of the reagent used for the fixation of sulphur. This indicates that the nature of the sulphur groups formed vary with the nature of the sulphuring reagent employed.

TABLE I

Recovery of sulphur from different charcoals on treatment with different oxidising agents

Description of the sample	Total sulphur fixed (millieq./g.)	Amount of sulphur recovered on treatment with (millieq./g.)			
		aqueous bromine	aqueous chlorine.	acidified KC10 ₃	hot nitric acid
400°-outgassed sugar charcoal					
treated with : CS ₂	9.30	0.14	0.16	0.17	0.48
-do- H ₂ S	7.00	1.03	2.85	—	3.18
-do- S	11.10	1.10	3.87	4.23	4.12
-do- SO ₂	16.60	3.88	10.27	13.47	15.07
400°-outgassed coconut charcoal					
treated with : CS ₂	11.00	0.07	0.06	nil	0.82
-do- H ₂ S	7.05	0.87	2.33	1.0	3.25
-do- S	10.50	1.10	4.05	2.09	4.86
-do- SO ₂	11.90	3.51	10.70	10.40	10.70
1000°-outgassed sugar charcoal					
treated with : CS ₂	5.00	0.04	nil	nil	0.36
-do- H ₂ S	5.50	0.12	0.90	0.58	1.55
-do- S	5.61	0.19	0.70	0.80	1.68
-do- SO ₂	5.40	1.77	4.90	5.00	5.31
1030°-outgassed coconut charcoal					
treated with: CS ₂	5.50	0.29	0.34	nil	0.32
-do- H ₂ S	4.30	0.45	0.81	0.70	0.65
-do- S	4.80	0.50	1.20	1.25	1.40
-do- SO ₂	4.20	1.53	3.75	3.90	4.10

The amount of sulphur recovered from carbon disulphide-treated charcoals, previously outgassed at 400° or 1000°, is seen to constitute only a small fraction, hardly 6-7 per cent of the total sulphur fixed even with most drastic oxidising solutions employed. Evidently, interaction of charcoal with carbon disulphide gives rise to highly stable surface compounds

of sulphur. Since in this interaction carbon is also deposited³ through the agency of hydrogen present in the charcoal

it is not unlikely that a new stable heterocyclic ring containing sulphur gets condensed on the multiple ring structure formed during pyrolysis in the preparation of charcoal. In any case sulphur seems to be fixed in the nucleus of the ring structure and not in any of the side chains so as to account for such a stability of the complex.

The results obtained with H_2S -treated charcoals indicate that the amount of sulphur equivalent to surface unsaturation, which is 3.8 and 3.7 millieq/g. for sugar and coconut charcoals respectively³, is fixed firmly as it is not released even on treatment with excess of hot concentrated nitric acid. This is true in the case of 400°-as well as 1000°-outgassed charcoals. The rest of the combined sulphur, the amount of which is in excess of surface unsaturation, in each case, gets released almost fully on oxidation with nitric acid and considerably even on treatment with chlorine water. It appears that quinonic and phenolic hydroxyl groups which are present in appreciable amounts, particularly in the case of 400°-outgassed charcoals³, are involved in the interaction with hydrogen sulphide giving rise to sulphide or hydrosulphide groups. Studebaker has indicated such possibilities². These groups, being attached to the side chains, are easily oxidisable. The sulphur fixed at the unsaturated sites probably gives rise to $\overset{\text{C}}{\text{C}}>\text{S}$ structures which are more stable. It is significant to note that the amount of sulphur released as sulphuric acid is much more in 400°-outgassed charcoals than in 1000°-outgassed charcoals. This is because the former category contains much more oxygen than the latter. However, the amount of sulphur that is not released is seen to be about the same in 400°-as well as in 1000°-outgassed charcoals. This is because surface unsaturation is about the same in these cases. It appears highly probable, therefore, that interaction of charcoal with hydrogen sulphide gives rise to the reactive sulphide and hydrosulphide groups as well as to unreactive $\overset{\text{C}}{\text{C}}>\text{S}$ groups.

The interaction of charcoal with sulphur vapour causes evolution of hydrogen sulphide as well¹. This treatment, therefore, involves combined action of hydrogen sulphide and sulphur vapour. The amount of sulphur fixed is accordingly more. In addition to the reactive and non-reactive groups formed with hydrogen sulphide discussed above, some of the sulphur is expected to be fixed up at the sites vacated by combined hydrogen. This sulphur, evidently, would not be easily oxidisable. At the same time a part of the sulphur may be fixed up at some of the active centres on the surface giving rise to sulphide groups in analogy with the formation of quinone groups on similar treatment with oxygen. This sulphur should be reactive and, therefore, oxidisable. Thus the amount of sulphur released as sulphuric acid as well as that not released is more in the case of sulphur-treated than in the case of H_2S -treated products.

Finally, it is interesting to note that almost the entire amount of sulphur fixed on treatment with sulphur dioxide is oxidisable, in some cases even by chlorine water. It appears that in this case the more readily oxidisable sulphone groups, in addition to equally

easily oxidisable sulphide and hydrosulphide groups, are formed. The formation of sulphone groups is supported by the fact that an appreciable amount of oxygen is also fixed along with sulphur on treatment of charcoals with sulphur dioxide¹.

It appears from the above discussions that the nature of sulphur groups formed on fixation of sulphur by charcoal depends, to a large extent, upon the nature of the sulphurising agent employed.

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Received, April 8, 1968.